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A KEY FOCUS ON HRD CLIMATE AND ITS IMPACT ON JOB SATISFACTION: A STUDY IN CEMENT INDUSTRY

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Abstract:

The human factor is considered as one of the most crucial and critical factor in the development of any country. Development does not occur spontaneously as a natural consequence, it is the human resource which acts as an agent or catalyst in bringing the required pace of development in any country. Therefore, human resources are required to be well developed, nurtured and properly organised in order to bring about prosperity in any country. The utmost care is to be given to the human resource as they are the index of development. Similarly, it has been said and simultaneously proved that the success of any organisation depends upon the quality and potential of its employees. Thus the human resources need to be taken well care of in any organisation that wishes to stand in this cut throat competitive era. The basic objective of a firm is to constantly innovate and develop in order to sustain and remain competitive in the globalised market. The basic strength of an organization comes from its research and the potential of an organisation enhances through development of organisational work force. This draws the basis for our research, the main objective of our research is to highlight & understand the impact of HRD climate over the Job satisfaction as an organisational performance measure in the cement industry of Jammu And Kashmir State. The findings of the present study reveal a definite impact of HRD Climate on job satisfaction which in turn influences the organisational performance.

Keywords: HRD Climate, Job satisfaction.

Introduction:

Human Resource Development continues to grow its importance within organisations due to change in organisations' approach of achieving competitive advantage and their focus to nurture and develop their strategic resources (employees). Human resource development is a people-oriented concept that focuses on developing the skills, knowledge and competencies of people. The concept of HRD was formally introduced by Prof. Dr. Leonard Nadler in 1969 in a conference organised by American Society of Training and Development (Rao, 2000). In India, Larson & Toubro Ltd. was the first company to introduce this concept in 1975 among private sector companies with an objective of facilitating growth of knowledge workers. Among the public sector government companies it was BHEL which introduced this concept in 1980. Human Resource plays an active role in the modern economic scenario of any country and their development in the organizational context is a process by which the employees of an organization are helped in a continuous and a planned way to: (a) acquire or sharpen capabilities required to perform various functions associated with their present or expected future roles; (b) develop their general capabilities as individuals and discover and exploit their own inner potentials for their own and/or organizational development processes; and (c) develop an organizational culture in which supervisor-subordinate relationships, team work and collaboration among sub-units are strong and contribute to the professional well-being, motivation and pride of employees (Rao and Abraham:1986). There is huge shift in organisations' orientation and organisations realized that a firm can survive in stiff competition through their valuable human resources. In this uncertain and globalized era there is huge demand for talented people. On the other hand employees' expectations and demands are changing and the organisations have to respond to meet their expectations and provide good developmental environment in order to have sustainable development through committed workforce. *Human Resource Development (HRD) Climate* is a concept proposed by T.V. Rao (1999) to explain the environment provided by organisations for the learning and development of its employees. This includes both the policies and the practices for HRD in an organisation. He developed an instrument to measure the HRD Climate by assessing three components such as the top management's commitment to HRD (general climate), existence of an OCTAPAC culture and the functioning of the various HRD subsystems. The OCTAPACE culture indicates the existence of eight factors namely, Openness, Confrontation, Trust, Autonomy, Pro-activity, Authenticity, and Collaboration and experimentation in an organisation. HRD mechanism, the third component of the HRD climate, measures the extent to which the various subsystems of the HRD mechanism such as training, performance appraisal, potential appraisal, organisation development, feedback and performance coaching, career planning, rewards, employee welfare, quality of work life and human resource information systems are implemented seriously (Rao, 1999).

Review of Literature:

The literature review presents the conclusions of various research studies conducted by different scholars and researchers. Various research studies have been conducted in the arena of HRD climate in different sectors and in relation to different variables, some of them are mentioned below:

A research study was carried out by **T. V. Rao and E. Abraham (1986)** among 41 organizations in India. The study found that the general HRD climate in the organizations appears to be at an average level. The most important factor contributing to this seems to be a general indifference on the part of the employees on their own development. This was followed by the top management's lip sympathy and intellectual positivism to HRD but no emotional investment.

In another study, **E. Abraham (1989)** found that HRD climate is a powerful intervening variable in translating HRD practices into profit.

Jain V K, Singhal K C and Singh V C (1996) conducted a study on "HRD Climate in Indian Industry" in two public sector organisations namely BHEL (Bharat Heavy Electricals Limited) and NFL (National Fertilizers Limited) and concluded that the HRD climate was mainly a function of the effectiveness. The

variables contributing the efficiency were individual efficiency, organisational efficiency and productivity, management policy on HRD, organisational development, role analysis and training.

Rohmetra(1998) studied HRD climate and satisfaction in State Bank of India (SBI) and The Jammu and Kashmir Bank Ltd. (JKB) and found that HRD climate was much higher in SBI than in JKB. Comparative analysis of the attitudes of employees towards the prevailing development climate revealed that employees in SBI held a much favourable attitude towards the development practices than that in JKB. Consequently, the satisfaction level of employees in SBI is higher than that in JKB.

Chalam and Srinivas (2005) in their study Gender wise Perceptions and Attitudes on HRD Climate in Indian Banking Sector; examined the basic disagreement with respect to HRD Climate in the selected branches of SBI.

Rodrigues (2005) opined in his article entitled “Industry-Institute correlates of HRD Climate- Empirical study based implications” that a well-trained and a well-educated human resource contributes directly to the development of a country and to improve the knowledge, abilities, aptitude and values of human beings organized HRD practices should be followed.

VijayaBanu (2007) in his study “A Study on HRD Climate with Special Reference to Public Sector Cement Corporation” concluded that to survive and excel in the new economy, the HRD climate is of crucial importance to the Indian public sector organizations.

PoojaPurang (2007) in a Comparative Analysis of HRD Climate in Public Private and Multinational Organizations concluded that the Employee perceptions regarding the Human Resource Development Climate are significantly better in the private sector and MNC in comparison to the Public Sector Organization.

Srimannarayana(2008) carried out a study to assess the extent of HRD climate prevailing in Indian organizations. He derives the conclusion that a moderate climate prevails in organizations under study (59.61%) and more favourable HRD climate was in manufacturing sector (62.39%) than in service & IT sectors.

Purang(2008) a favourable climate influences directly the behaviour of employees in an organization which creates a sense of belongingness in them and also enables them to perform well.

Hyde *et al.* (2008) conducted an exploratory survey of HRD Climate in private sector banks. The authors suggested developing and maintaining the dyadic relations at work and supportive guidance should be provided by seniors to their juniors in creating a congenial working atmosphere which will also help in developing human resource in an organized manner.

Rao(2009) carried out a study on HRD climate in the thermal Power Station of Vijayawada in Andhra Pradesh and stated through his study that HRD is a process which helps to develop and identify the keen potential of human force. He further suggested that the management in an organization should be generous and should also support their work force emotionally so that it will help the employees to work better and enable them to exhibit their knowledge and skills in a cohesive manner.

Solkheand Chaudhary(2010) studied the Impact of HRD Climate over Job satisfaction measures to improve the Organizational Performance. Sample size chosen for the study was 100 employees out of which only 71 responded through a 38 items model questionnaire developed by Rao and Abraham for analysing the trends in HRD Climate.

Subramaniand Jan (2011) discussed the importance of the efficiency of human resource in the success of any organization in their published research paper. The authors emphasized their work over the study of organizational climate in IT industries of Chennai, authors suggested to improve the organizational climatic conditions to match the requirements of the organizational development.

Mukeshkumarparsahar (2012) carried out a study to assess the perception of employees regarding HRD climate prevailing in the shrivaishnav institute of technology and science a private college in Indore on the basis of their age group and came up with the conclusion that there was no significant difference in the perception of the employees belonging to different age groups about prevailing HRD climate in the said institute.

Benjamin (2012) in his paper examined the relationships among human resource development climate (HRDC), organizational Citizenship behaviour (OCB) and voluntary turnover intentions (VTI) in Nigerian banks. He found Nigerian banks management can reduce turnover and foster citizenship behaviour by ensuring that a favourable developmental climate exists within their organization.

Sekar, Muttiah and Santosh (2012) presented the HRD Climate of workers in Indian manufacturing companies. They found the existence of average climate for development in these organizations.

Rationale of the study:

Manufacturing sector is one of the most important sectors of the economy. It contributes significantly in the development process of the nation. Manufacturing industries have uniqueness in terms of product line, work force requirements, trade unionism, infrastructure, statutory implications, expense overheads, work division, working hours and a host of other factors which makes it different from other sectors. All these mentioned factors have an implication on the organization's ability to create a HRD Climate which fulfils the needs of the employees that satisfies them in order to finish or complete their assigned roles and perform to the best of their abilities and contribute to organizational success. A research based study which attempts to find out the state of HRD Climate, level of satisfaction of the employees and correlation between the two in manufacturing organizations is very much needed. This calls for the study to find out the impact of various factors on HRD climate and job satisfaction and also how the HRD Climate impacts employee satisfaction and thereby organizational performance of the cement manufacturing undertakings in the state of J&K.

Objectives of the study:

In light of the realm for research, the study was undertaken:

- To examine the nature of the HRD Climate existing in the cement industry of Kashmir region.
- To study the level of Job Satisfaction of the employees in the said industry.
- To critically analyse the relationship of HRD Climate and Job Satisfaction and subsequently the impact of HRD climate on job satisfaction of the employees.

HYPOTHESIS:

In view of the objectives set for the study, following null hypothesis was formulated:

Ho: There is no significant relationship between HRD Climate and the level of job satisfaction of the employees in the cement industry.

Research design:

Sampling: For the purposes of the study, researcher selected the cement industry of Kashmir region (Khyber, SAIFCO, TCI, CemTac and JK cements). The survey research design method was used in this study. It involves the use of questionnaire in collecting data from the respondents. A total of 80 employees belonging to five cement factories located in Khrew area of Kashmir responded to only 71 questionnaires which measured the following variables: Human Resource Development Climate and job satisfaction. Therefore with the 71% response rate researcher has conducted the present study.

Instrument: The research instruments used in the study are: HRD climate survey Questionnaire and job satisfaction Questionnaire. The HRD climate survey questionnaire was developed by **T.V. Rao and E. Abraham (1985)** at the XLRI Centre for HRD. This 38-item instrument is widely being used to survey the organisational HRD climate. It is a 38-item questionnaire that assesses an organisation's general climate, prevailing culture as well as the implementation of HRD mechanism or policies. Job Satisfaction Scale developed by **C.N. Daftuar(1997)** consisting of 19 items (out of which two items measure separately overall satisfaction with the company and overall satisfaction with the work) was used for the purpose. The respondents were asked to rate each statement on a five-point scale ranging from 5 (strongly agree) to 1 (strongly disagree).

Reliability of the scales: Alpha (Cronbach's) reliability of the two scales used is

HRD Climate Scale = .96, Job Satisfaction = .95

This indicates a very high internal reliability, based on average inter-item correlation.

Statistical measures: To analyse the results, various statistical tools like mean, standard deviation, regression, correlation were applied through SPSS 16 and MS EXCEL 2007.

ANALYSIS: General Climate:

The item wise mean scores of the total sample of 71 employees are presented in the table 1.

TABLE 1: General climate

SNO.	STATEMENT	MEAN	ST.DEV
1	<i>The top management of this organisation goes out of its way to make sure that employees enjoy their work.</i>	2.6620	1.02739
2	<i>The top management believes that human resources are an extremely important resource and that they have to be treated more humanly.</i>	3.3521	0.98704
3	<i>Development of the subordinates is seen as an important part of their job by the employees/officers here.</i>	3.3944	0.91774
4	<i>The personnel policies in this organization facilitate employee development.</i>	3.0845	1.06565
5	<i>The top management Is willing to invest a considerable part of their time and other resources to ensure the development of employees.</i>	2.9718	1.08195
6	<i>Senior officers/executives in this organization take active Interest in their juniors and help them learn their job.</i>	3.3521	1.05693
7	<i>People lacking competence in doing their jobs are helped to acquire competence rather than being left unattended.</i>	3.1690	0.86166
8	<i>Employees in this organization believe that employee behaviour can be changed and people can be developed at any stage of their life.</i>	3.5352	1.09324
9	<i>People in this organization are helpful to each other.</i>	3.7887	0.96976
10	<i>Employees in this organization are very informal and do not hesitate to discuss their personal problems with their supervisors.</i>	3.7183	0.92864
11	<i>The psychological climate in this organization is very conducive to any employee interested in developing himself by acquiring new knowledge and skills.</i>	3.5070	1.01240
12	<i>Seniors guide their juniors and prepare them for future responsibilities/ roles they are likely to take up.</i>	3.3944	0.97803
13	<i>The top management of this industry makes efforts to identify and utilize the potential of the employees</i>	2.9577	1.12677
18	<i>People in this industry do not have any fixed mental impression/mental reservations about each other.</i>	3.2817	0.95891
	<i>Over all general climate</i>	3.29	0.56450

Since the questionnaire used 5 point scale, where mean score of 1 indicates extremely poor HRD Climate and of 5 extremely excellent HRD climate. Mean score of 2 indicates poor HRD Climate, Average mean score 3 indicate a moderate tendency on that dimension. Scores around 4 indicate a fairly good degree of existence. Examining the three major components of HRD Climate i.e. General Climate, HRD Mechanisms and OCTAPAC Culture the results indicates:

The General Climate Dimension as per Table 1 depicts higher mean scores for Item No.9 (3.78), 10 (3.71) and 8 (3.53) than other items which indicate that employees in the cement industry of Kashmir are helpful and informal to each other and do not hesitate to discuss their personal problems with their supervisors and senior employees. This industry believes that employees' behaviour can be changed and people can be developed at any stage of their life.

TABLE: 2 HRD MECHANISMS

SNO.	STATEMENT	MEAN	STAD.DEV.
14	<i>Promotion decisions are based on the suitability of the promotion rather than on favouritism.</i>	2.6620	1.12051
15	<i>There are mechanisms in this organization to reward any good work done or any contribution made by employees.</i>	3.1549	1.10386
16	<i>An employee is appreciated by his supervisors when he does good work.</i>	3.5915	1.00822
17	<i>Performance appraisal reports in our organization are based on objective assessment and adequate information and not on any favouritism.</i>	3.2535	1.03811
19	<i>Employees are encouraged to experiment with and try out new methods and try out creative ideas.</i>	3.1268	1.19439
20	<i>When any employee makes a mistake his supervisors treat it with understanding and help him to learn from such mistakes rather than punishing him or discouraging him.</i>	3.4930	0.96914
21	<i>Weaknesses of employees are communicated to them in a non-threatening way.</i>	3.4789	0.92364
22	<i>When behaviour feedback is given to employees they take it seriously and use it for development.</i>	3.1127	0.90316
23	<i>Employees in this organization take pains to find out their strengths and weaknesses from their supervising officers or colleagues.</i>	2.9296	0.97576
24	<i>When employees are sponsored for training, they take it seriously and try to learn from the programmes they attend.</i>	3.4366	1.10496
25	<i>Employees returning from training programmes are given opportunities to try out what they have learnt.</i>	3.2958	0.99131
26	<i>Employees are sponsored for training programmes on the basis of genuine training needs.</i>	3.3380	1.09471
37	<i>This organization ensures employee's welfare to such an extent that the employees can save a lot of their mental energy for work purposes.</i>	2.8873	0.90316
38	<i>Job-rotation in this organization facilitates employee development.</i>	3.1690	1.06886
	Overall HRDM	3.20	0.62879

In the HRD Mechanisms table 2, mean scores for Item No.16 (3.59), 19 (3.49) Item no. 20 (3.47) and Item No. 23 (3.43) were found higher than other items which indicates that the employees are quite satisfied with the reward and recognition programmes, learning and Development activities, Feedback mechanisms and most importantly Training activities. This shows that company is having a reasonable level of development orientation and employees are contented with the same. On the other side the employees were quite dissatisfied with respect to the promotion decisions in the company as per item no.14 (2.66).

As per the table 3 of OCTAPAC Values, the mean score for Item No.26 (3.67), 28 (3.56) and Item No. 33 (3.49) was found to be higher than other items which indicates that employees in this industry trust each other and they are not afraid to express or discuss the feelings with their subordinates, they confront their problem rather than accusing each other behind the back.

Table: 3 OCTAPAC CULTURE

SNO.	STATEMENT	MEAN	STAD.DEV
27	People trust each other in this organization.	3.6761	0.92234
28	Employees do not feel afraid about their expression of/ or discussion of their feelings with their superiors.	3.3239	0.96769
29	Employees are not afraid to express or discuss their feelings with their subordinates.	3.5634	0.90605
30	Employees are encouraged to take initiative and do things on their own without having to wait for instructions from supervisors.	3.1268	1.04101
31	Delegation of authority to encourage juniors to develop handling higher responsibilities is quite common in this organization.	3.0845	1.07897
32	When seniors delegate authority to juniors, the juniors use it as an opportunity for development.	3.3803	0.88425
33	When seniors delegate authority to juniors, the juniors use it as an opportunity for development.	3.3803	0.88425
34	When problems arise people discuss these problems openly and try to solve them rather than keep accusing each other behind the back.	3.4930	0.89240
35	Career opportunities are pointed out to juniors by senior officers in the organization.	2.7746	1.05826
36	The organization's future plans are made known to the managerial staff to help them develop their juniors and prepare them for future.	2.9437	1.08084
	Overall OCTAPAC CULTURE	3.27	0.57581

Here the overall mean score of HRD Climate was calculated to be 3.25 (56.25%) which indicate the existence of a just above average degree of HRD Climate.

Table: 4 overall HRD climates

SNO.	HRD ELEMENTS	MEAN	STAD.DEV
1	GENERAL CLIMATE	3.29	0.56450
2	HRD MECAHISM	3.20	0.62879
3	OCTAPAC CULTURE	3.27	0.57581
	OVER ALL HRD CLIMATE	3.25	0.53230

Job Satisfaction

The item wise mean scores of the total sample of 71 employees are presented in the Table 5.

Since the questionnaire used 5 point scale, ranging from 5 strongly agree to 1 strongly disagree. Here the overall score was 3.27 which indicate that job satisfaction level of employees is just above average. Examining the scores of the individual items of the JS Scale, the researcher found that the mean scores of the items no.1 (3.76), 5(3.70),4 (3.69) and 18(3.56) are higher than other items in the scale which indicates that the employees are highly satisfied with the availability as well as adequacy of opportunities to do different things from time to time which make use of their abilities along with this they are also contended with the stability in employment .On the whole the results showed that people are happy with the work and the organization in general.

Table 5: Daftuar's Job Satisfaction Scale:

SNO.	STATEMENT	MEAN	S.D
1	My job provides adequate opportunities to do different things from time to time.	3.7606	0.86956
2	My job provides adequate opportunities to be "some body" in the community.	3.4085	0.80316
3	My supervisor is quite competent in making decisions.	3.4648	0.99758
4	My Job provides for stable employment in suitable ways.	3.6901	0.97967
5	My job provides adequate opportunities to do something that makes use of my abilities.	3.7042	1.03364

6	<i>My job provides fair Pay.</i>	2.3662	1.09856
7	<i>My job provides adequate opportunities for advancement on this job.</i>	3.0423	0.93253
8	<i>I'm happy with the working conditions.</i>	2.9155	1.06565
9	<i>I'm happy with the way my co-workers get along with each other.</i>	3.3803	0.86794
10	<i>My Job provides me a feeling of accomplishment.</i>	3.4789	0.90805
11	<i>I'm happy with the General management of the company.</i>	3.2113	1.06792
12	<i>I'm happy with my past advancements' in this organization.</i>	3.2817	0.92864
13	<i>There are adequate opportunities for future growth (in efficiency).</i>	2.8451	0.98049
14	<i>Social conditions are appropriate for the job with in the organization.</i>	3.2394	0.94815
15	<i>My work is suitably recognized in the organization.</i>	3.3521	1.04333
16	<i>I'm happy with the kind and amount of responsibilities assigned to me.</i>	3.3803	0.93145
17	<i>I'm happy with the Company's policies.</i>	2.9577	1.07486
18	<i>I'm happy with my work as a whole.</i>	3.5634	0.95218
19	<i>I'm happy with my company/organization as a whole.</i>	3.2394	1.11438
	<i>Overall job satisfaction</i>	3.27	0.53984

Relationship between Climate and Job Satisfaction

Mean score analysis of HRD climate and Job satisfaction of the organization reveal that a relationship exists between them. Correlation analysis was carried out to test their relationship statistically (Table 6).The result shows that a significant positive correlation of 0.786 exists between them. Therefore, it supports the hypothesis and makes clear that an improvement in

HRD Climate is essential for improving the level of job satisfaction of the employees, which in turn will bring positive changes in Organizational Performance of the company. Having observed that a positive correlation exists between the HRD Climate and JS, further analysis was conducted to find the relationship between the sub factors or dimensions of HRD Climate with Job Satisfaction (Table 6).

Table 6: Correlation Results between Job Satisfaction and HRD Climate, its Components (General Climate, OCTAPAC Culture and HRD Mechanisms).

SNO.	PEARSON CORRELATION SIG. (2-TAILED) N	HRDC	JS	GC	HRDM	OC
1	HRDC	1	.786** .000	.887** .000	.912** .000	.901** .000
		71	71	71	71	71
2	JS	.786** .000	1	.734** .000	.693** .000	.695** .000
		71	71	71	71	71
3	GC	.887** .000	.734** .000	1	.664** .000	.729** .000
		71	71	71	71	71
4	HRDM	.912** .000	.693** .000	.664** .000	1	.763** .000
		71	71	71	71	71
5	OC	.901 .000	.695** .000	.729 .000	.763** .000	1
		71	71	71	71	71

The correlational analysis performed to analyse the relationship between HRD Climate Dimensions i.e. General Climate, HRD Mechanisms and OCTAPAC Culture and Job Satisfaction. The analysis showed

that there exists a positive relationship between different components of HRD Climate and Job satisfaction. The correlation coefficient was .734 (JS*General Climate), .693 (JS*HRD Mechanisms) and .695 (JS*OCTAPAC Culture) respectively.

This proves that HRD Climate is a contributing/influencing factor to increase the level of job satisfaction of the employees.

Impact of Climate on Job Satisfaction

Regression analysis was performed to explain the impact of HRD Climate on job satisfaction i.e. the amount of association. F –Value of 111.56 which is significant at 5% level of significance proves that the regression model is valid. (Table 7). The individual impact of HRD Climate dimensions on satisfaction cannot be interpreted in this analysis because of the existence of multi-co linearity and high inter-item correlation, which may distract the results. But however it can be said that job satisfaction is very much influenced by General Climate, HRD Mechanisms and OCTAPAC Culture in general. The results may differ according to the settings. It was found during the regression analysis that 61% of the variance in job satisfaction is explained by the HRD Climate variables. Therefore the null hypothesis that there does not exist any relationship between HRD Climate and the level of job satisfaction of the employees in the organization is rejected.

Table 7: result of Regression model of HRDC on JS.

MODEL SUMMARY									
SNO.	R	R SQUARE	ADJUSTED R SQUARE	STD ERROR OF THE ESTIMATE	CHANGE STATISTICS				
					R SQUARE CHANGE	F CHANGE	DF1	DF2	SIG.F CHANGE
1	0.786 ^a	0.618	0.612	0.33612	0.618	111.567	1	69	.000

a: Predictors: (Constant), HRDC.

CONCLUSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS:

Capable and talented employees can be retained in any organisation provided if there exists conducive HRD Climate. In the present study, the researcher finds the existence of good HRD Climate in the cement industry of Kashmir region, according to the perceptions of employees sought through the scale constructed for measuring the same. The employees in general showed a favourable attitude towards HRD Policies and practices of the organization. They were satisfied with the developmental policies of the top management as well as contented with their work and the organization as a whole i.e. level of job satisfaction was also good. Most importantly the researchers’ findings support the existing literature and add to the deficit literature existing which have attempted to explore the relationship of HRD Climate and Job Satisfaction in Indian Context. It was concluded that there is a significant relationship between JS and HRDC and any positive change in HRD Climate and its components will bring about positive changes in Job Satisfaction and in turn impact the Organizational Performance in positive manner.

However the findings of the present study indicate that there is a still substantial scope for improvement in various aspects of HRD in the organization as well as factors influencing Job Satisfaction.

Some of these aspects along with broad suggestions are:-

- The top management’s commitment should be increased towards learning & potential development of its human resources in all its endeavours. The mean score of the items dealing with these aspects were 2.66, 2.97 and 2.95 which are below average.

- Management should also draw its attention towards bringing reforms in the Promotion policy (2.66) as well as the welfare practices of the organization (2.88), as the mean score is quite below average on these two HRD mechanisms.
- In general psychological climate in the organization should be improved and efforts should be initiated to make it conducive to the development of employees. Besides, there is an urgent need for restructuring the various personnel policies in the organization. Sound personnel policies that show high concern for employees and emphasise equity and objectivity in appraisals would go a long way in creating a better HRD Climate in the organization. The management should also take a good look at the existing HRD mechanisms and explore the possibilities of introducing new ones.
- On account of satisfaction level of employees certain improvements derives the attention the organization needs to improve the working conditions, needs to revise the compensation packages as per the industry standards, career opportunities should be pointed out to employees ,company policies should be conveyed in a simplified manner and its interpretation should be checked through feedback mechanisms as the mean scores was low in these categories respectively (2.36, 2.91, 2.95 and 2.84)

Scope and limitations of the study:

In the end it must be emphasized here that since this study was carried out in a manufacturing organization, the findings of the study are not applicable to other types of organizations. Although this study was made as an attempt in examining the potential impact of HRD Climate on Organizational Performance by concentrating on single variable i.e. just job satisfaction, but there are many other indicators of OP such as Financial Performance, Employee Turnover, Market Performance, Sales Turnover, Productivity which remains unconsidered. Thus, there is a scope for further research in this area. In general, this study contributes to the literature on HRD Climate and provides an additional insight to the individuals associated with the HR field.

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